

THREE-DIMENSIONAL FLOATING NODE METHOD FOR MODELLING PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE AND FAILURE IN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper extends the previously proposed Floating Node Method (FNM) into a three-dimensional (3D) formulation; the 3D FNM aims to model explicitly the matrix crack, delamination as well as their intersections, such that the matrix crack/delamination interaction mechanism can be captured. The FNM uses the Degrees of Freedom (DoF) of extra nodes to represent the DoF of cracks; the extra nodes are not confined to the existing nodal positions; their initial coordinates do not participate in the finite element calculation and can be anywhere in the domain (hence the name floating node). The FNM enables the flexible association of floating nodes with the geometrical features of the element (such as edges), such that complex elements, which can modify their geometrical features with the associated floating DoF during analysis, can be formed.

1 INTRODUCTION

The progressive damage and failure of composite laminates is typically preceded by an accumulation of numerous matrix cracks and delamination, which interact with each other to form a complex network of cracks. In many cases, predicting the development of this matrix crack/delamination network is critical for the reliable prediction of the ultimate failure. Despite the importance of the matrix crack/delamination interaction shown in the literature [1, 2, 3, 4], the realistic modelling of the kinematics of this interaction still poses a challenge, especially for 3D problems. This paper extends the previously developed Floating Node Method (FNM) [5, 6] into a 3D formulation; the 3D FNM aims to model explicitly the matrix crack, delamination as well as their intersections, such that the interaction mechanism can be captured.

2 THEORY

The FNM is developed based on the Phantom Node Method (PNM) [7, 8, 9, 10]. Similarly to the PNM, the FNM uses the Degrees of Freedom (DoF) of extra nodes to represent the DoF of cracks; unlike the PNM, the FNM extra nodes are not confined to the existing nodal positions; their initial coordinates do not participate in the finite element calculation and can be anywhere in the domain (hence the name floating node). The FNM enables the flexible association of floating nodes with the geometrical features of the element (such as edges, surfaces, interfaces and volumes, etc.). Complex elements, which modify in situ their geometrical features using the associated floating DoFs, can be formed using the FNM [5, 6]. The rest of the paper demonstrates the FNM for the modelling of a 3D composite laminate.

2.1 FNM ply element

Figure 1: 3D FNM ply element topology and partitioning

A 3D FNM ply element is formulated to model matrix cracking, based on the 2D one in [5]. Figure 1(a) shows the topology of such an element. It is composed of 24 nodes in total. Nodes 1-8 represent the vertices of the brick. Two floating nodes are allocated to each potentially-breakable edge of the element (for simplicity, it is assumed that matrix cracks only traverse the horizontal edges). Note that the coordinates of these floating nodes are initially undetermined. All the floating nodes are shared with neighbour elements through their common edges. When a matrix crack needs to be modelled within its domain, the FNM ply element can be partitioned into sub-elements (SE) as shown in Figure 1(b-c), by using the associated floating nodes on the cracked edges to represent the DoF of crack points on the edges.

Before crack initiation, the FNM ply element is the same as a standard linear brick element. The weak form of the equilibrium equation in the element domain Ω is:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} \, d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{b} \, d\Omega + \int_{\partial\Omega} \delta \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{f} \, d\partial\Omega, \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ are the strain and stress tensors, \mathbf{q} is the DoF vector, \mathbf{b} is the body force and \mathbf{f} the surface traction.

The coordinates \mathbf{x} of a point in the physical domain Ω is interpolated from nodal coordinates \mathbf{x}_N using polynomial shape functions defined on a natural domain \mathbf{A} (with coordinates \mathbf{a}):

$$\mathbf{x}(\mathbf{a}) = \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{a}) \mathbf{x}_N, \quad \mathbf{x}_N = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_8\}^T, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{N} is the brick element shape function matrix. In the isoparametric formulation, the DoF vector \mathbf{q} of the element is interpolated from the nodal DoF vectors \mathbf{q}_N using the same shape function matrix \mathbf{N} :

$$\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{a}) = \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{a}) \mathbf{q}_N, \quad \mathbf{q}_N = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_8\}^T. \quad (3)$$

The linear elastic strain $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is obtained from the DoF vector \mathbf{q} through a linear operator L :

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = L(\mathbf{q}) = L_N(\mathbf{q}_N) = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{q}_N, \quad \mathbf{B} = L_N(\mathbf{N}), \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{B} is the strain-displacement matrix.

The linear elastic stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ at the strain $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{D} is the material stiffness matrix.

Substituting equations (2) to (5) to the weak form (1), the discretized finite element equilibrium equation can be obtained:

$$\mathbf{K} \mathbf{q}_N = \mathbf{F}, \quad (6)$$

where the element's stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} is:

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} d\Omega = \int_A \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \det(\mathbf{J}) dA, \quad (7)$$

and the force vector \mathbf{F} is:

$$\mathbf{F} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{b} d\Omega + \int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{f} d\partial\Omega = \int_A \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{b} \det(\mathbf{J}) dA + \int_{\partial A} \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{f} \det(\mathbf{J}) d\partial A, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{J} is the Jacobian matrix between the physical domain Ω and the natural domain A :

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \mathbf{a}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}}{\partial \mathbf{a}} \mathbf{x}_N. \quad (9)$$

Note that the coordinates of the nodes \mathbf{x}_N only participates in the calculation of the element stiffness matrix through the Jacobian \mathbf{J} . In this partition, the floating nodes are not used. Their associated terms can be crossed out from the global system equations. Otherwise, each floating node can be assigned with a dummy stiffness to avoid having a singular stiffness matrix.

After matrix crack initiates within or propagates into the element domain, the original domain Ω is split into Ω_1 , Ω_2 and the interface Γ , as the element domains of SE1, SE2 and SE3, respectively. SE1 and SE2 are standard linear brick elements and SE3 is a cohesive element (Figure 1(b)). The crack coordinates on the cracked edges, \mathbf{x}_i^c , \mathbf{x}_j^c , \mathbf{x}_k^c and \mathbf{x}_l^c , can be calculated from the material's failure criterion. The nodal coordinates of the three SEs are therefore fully defined (and hence also the Jacobians):

$$\mathbf{x}_N^{SE1} = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_i^c, \mathbf{x}_j^c, \mathbf{x}_4, \mathbf{x}_5, \mathbf{x}_k^c, \mathbf{x}_l^c, \mathbf{x}_8\}^T, \quad \mathbf{J}^{SE1} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}^{SE1}}{\partial \mathbf{a}} \mathbf{x}_N^{SE1}, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_N^{SE2} = \{\mathbf{x}_i^c, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3, \mathbf{x}_j^c, \mathbf{x}_k^c, \mathbf{x}_6, \mathbf{x}_7, \mathbf{x}_l^c\}^T, \quad \mathbf{J}^{SE2} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}^{SE2}}{\partial \mathbf{a}} \mathbf{x}_N^{SE2}, \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_N^{SE3} = \{\mathbf{x}_i^c, \mathbf{x}_j^c, \mathbf{x}_k^c, \mathbf{x}_l^c\}^T, \quad \mathbf{J}^{SE3} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}^{SE3}}{\partial \mathbf{a}} \mathbf{x}_N^{SE3}. \quad (12)$$

\mathbf{N}^{SEi} , $i=1,2,3$ are the shape function matrices of the three SEs. In this case, \mathbf{N}^{SE1} and \mathbf{N}^{SE2} are the linear brick element shape function matrix, and \mathbf{N}^{SE3} is the 8-node cohesive element shape function matrix. In the FNM, the nodal DoF vectors of these SEs are formed with the DoF of the floating nodes associated with the respective cracked edges. In this case, the DoF of the floating nodes 9, 10, 13, 14, 17, 18, 21 and 22 are used. The corresponding nodal DoF vectors of the three SEs are:

$$\mathbf{q}_N^{\text{SE1}} = \{\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{q}_9, \mathbf{q}_{14}, \mathbf{q}_4, \mathbf{q}_5, \mathbf{q}_{17}, \mathbf{q}_{22}, \mathbf{q}_8\}^T, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_N^{\text{SE2}} = \{\mathbf{q}_{10}, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{q}_3, \mathbf{q}_{13}, \mathbf{q}_{18}, \mathbf{q}_6, \mathbf{q}_7, \mathbf{q}_{21}\}^T, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_N^{\text{SE3}} = \{\mathbf{q}_9, \mathbf{q}_{14}, \mathbf{q}_{22}, \mathbf{q}_{17}, \mathbf{q}_{10}, \mathbf{q}_{13}, \mathbf{q}_{21}, \mathbf{q}_{18}\}^T. \quad (15)$$

Note that the nodal DoF vector of the cohesive SE (SE3) is entirely formed by the floating DoF. With equations (10)-(15), all the quantities needed for the integration of SE system equations are available. For SE1 and SE2, the integration follows the standard linear brick element formulation detailed in equations (2)-(9). For SE3, the integration follows the same procedure for a standard 8-node linear cohesive element. The weak form of equilibrium equation on the interface Γ is:

$$\int_{\Gamma} \delta[\mathbf{q}]^T \boldsymbol{\tau} \, d\Gamma = \int_{\Gamma} \delta[\mathbf{q}]^T \mathbf{b} \, d\Gamma + \int_{\partial\Gamma} \delta[\mathbf{q}]^T \mathbf{f} \, d\partial\Gamma, \quad (16)$$

where $[\mathbf{q}]$ is the jump vector of DoF across the interface Γ and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the cohesive traction. The shape functions corresponding to the four nodes of the rectangular interface are N_i , $i = 1 \sim 4$, and the matrix \mathbf{N}_{CE} of the eight-node cohesive element which relates $[\mathbf{q}]$ to the nodal DoF vector \mathbf{q}_N is:

$$\mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}} = [-\mathbf{N}, \mathbf{N}], \text{ where } \mathbf{N} = [N_i, i = 1 \sim 4]. \quad (17)$$

$[\mathbf{q}]$ is calculated from \mathbf{q}_N as:

$$[\mathbf{q}] = \mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}} \mathbf{q}_N. \quad (18)$$

The cohesive traction $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is calculated from the cohesive constitutive matrix \mathbf{D}_{CE} and $[\mathbf{q}]$ using:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{D}_{\text{CE}} [\mathbf{q}]. \quad (19)$$

Note that \mathbf{D}_{CE} is usually a function of $[\mathbf{q}]$ (i.e., the cohesive law). The weak form in (16) can be written into a discretized form for finite element implementation as the following:

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{CE}} \mathbf{q}_N = \mathbf{F}_{\text{CE}} \quad (20)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{CE}} = \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}}^T \mathbf{D}_{\text{CE}} \mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}} \, d\Gamma = \int_S \mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}}^T \mathbf{D}_{\text{CE}} \mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}} \det(\mathbf{J}_{\text{CE}}) \, dS \quad (21)$$

and

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{CE}} = \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}}^T \mathbf{b} \, d\Gamma + \int_{\partial\Gamma} \mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}}^T \mathbf{f} \, d\partial\Gamma = \int_S \mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}}^T \mathbf{b} \det(\mathbf{J}_{\text{CE}}) \, dS + \int_{\partial S} \mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}}^T \mathbf{f} \det(\mathbf{J}_{\text{CE}}) \, d\partial S. \quad (22)$$

\mathbf{J}_{CE} is the Jacobian matrix between physical domain Γ and natural domain S of the cohesive element:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\text{CE}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \mathbf{a}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}_{\text{CE}}}{\partial \mathbf{a}} \mathbf{x}_N. \quad (23)$$

The cohesive elements in this work are integrated using the Newton-Cotes method.

After integrating each of the SEs, the system matrices of the FNM ply element under this partition is simply the assembly of those of the SEs:

$$\mathbf{K} = \sum \mathbf{K}^{\text{SE}i}, \quad \mathbf{F} = \sum \mathbf{F}^{\text{SE}i}, \quad (24)$$

where $i = 1 \sim 3$ and $\mathbf{K}^{\text{SE}i}$ and $\mathbf{F}^{\text{SE}i}$ are respectively the stiffness matrices and force vectors of the three SEs.

2.2 FNM cohesive element

Figure 2: 3D FNM cohesive element topology and partitioning

It has been shown in the literature that explicitly representing the matrix crack edges on the interface cohesive element improves significantly the prediction of stress concentration at the intersection of matrix crack and the interface, and in turn predicts more accurately the subsequent delamination [11, 5, 6]. In this paper, a 3D FNM cohesive element is proposed, based on the 2D one in [5]. The nodal connectivity of the element is shown in Figure 2(a). The element is composed of 24 nodes. 8 real nodes are the standard cohesive element vertices and 16 floating nodes are associated with the 8 breakable edges which are parallel to the interface; these breakable edges are shared with the upper and lower FNM ply elements. Based on the partitions of the upper and lower FNM ply elements, the FNM cohesive element is partitioned accordingly to explicitly represent the matrix crack edges on the interface.

Before any matrix crack in the top and bottom plies, the FNM cohesive element is a standard 8-node linear cohesive element. Its nodal coordinate vector is:

$$\mathbf{x}_N = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_8\}^T, \quad (25)$$

and nodal DoF vector is:

$$\mathbf{q}_N = \{\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \dots, \mathbf{q}_8\}^T. \quad (26)$$

The integration of this cohesive element follows the procedure detailed in equations (16)-(23). In this partition, the floating nodes are not used; their associated terms can be crossed out from the global system equations or assigned with a dummy stiffness to avoid having a singular stiffness matrix.

After matrix cracks appear in the FNM ply elements, the FNM cohesive element is partitioned to represent the matrix crack edges. If the top ply has a matrix crack, then the FNM cohesive element is partitioned to SE1 as shown in in Figure 2(c). Similarly, if the bottom ply has a matrix crack, then the partition is SE2 in Figure 2(d). If both plies are cracked, then SE1 and SE2 are superimposed, each caring half the weight in integration. Each of the two SEs has 16 nodes, i.e., the 8 real nodes and 8 floating nodes on one of the two surfaces. SE1 has the 8 floating nodes of the upper cohesive surface and SE2 has those of the lower one. When the upper ply element has a matrix crack and partitions into sub-elements, SE1 partitions into SE1a and SE1b to explicitly represent the matrix crack edge on the interface (Figure 2(c)). The nodal coordinate vectors of SE1a and SE1b are:

$$\mathbf{x}_N^{\text{SE1a}} = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_{25}, \mathbf{x}_{26}, \mathbf{x}_4, \mathbf{x}_5, \mathbf{x}_{17}, \mathbf{x}_{22}, \mathbf{x}_8\}^T, \quad (27)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_N^{\text{SE1b}} = \{\mathbf{x}_{25}, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3, \mathbf{x}_{26}, \mathbf{x}_{18}, \mathbf{x}_6, \mathbf{x}_7, \mathbf{x}_{21}\}^T, \quad (28)$$

and the nodal DoF vectors of SE1a and SE1b are:

$$\mathbf{q}_N^{\text{SE1a}} = \{\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{q}_{25}, \mathbf{q}_{26}, \mathbf{q}_4, \mathbf{q}_5, \mathbf{q}_{17}, \mathbf{q}_{22}, \mathbf{q}_8\}^T, \quad (29)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_N^{\text{SE1b}} = \{\mathbf{q}_{25}, \mathbf{q}_2, \mathbf{q}_3, \mathbf{q}_{26}, \mathbf{q}_{18}, \mathbf{q}_6, \mathbf{q}_7, \mathbf{q}_{21}\}^T. \quad (30)$$

Note that nodes 25 and 26 are dummy nodes. Their coordinates are simply the top ply matrix crack coordinates projected on the bottom cohesive surface and their DoF vectors are interpolated from those of node-pair (1, 2) and (3, 4), respectively (Figure 2(c)). With these nodal vectors defined, the integrations of SE1a and SE1b follow the steps detailed in equations (16) to (23). The stiffness matrix and force vector of SE1, i.e., \mathbf{K}^{SE1} and \mathbf{F}^{SE1} , are the assembly of those of SE1a and SE1b:

$$\mathbf{K}^{\text{SE1}} = \mathbf{K}^{\text{SE1a}} + \mathbf{K}^{\text{SE1b}}, \quad \mathbf{F}^{\text{SE1}} = \mathbf{F}^{\text{SE1a}} + \mathbf{F}^{\text{SE1b}}. \quad (31)$$

Similarly, when the lower ply element has a matrix crack and partitions into sub-elements, SE2 further partitions into sub-elements SE2a and SE2b to explicitly represent the matrix crack edge on the interface (Figure 2(d)). As in the case of SE1, the nodal coordinate vectors and DoF vectors of SE2a and SE2b can be defined and the integrations can be performed. The stiffness matrix and force vector of SE2, i.e., \mathbf{K}^{SE2} and \mathbf{F}^{SE2} , are the assembly of those of SE2a and SE2b.

When both the top and the bottom plies have matrix cracks, both SE1 and SE2 are present. Because SE1 and SE2 are super-imposing each other, their energies are integrated over the same material domain. Therefore, the eventual stiffness matrix and force vector of the FNM cohesive element are the superposition of those of SE1 and SE2, each bearing half the weight of contribution:

$$\mathbf{K} = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{K}^{\text{SE1}} + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{K}^{\text{SE2}}, \quad \mathbf{F} = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{F}^{\text{SE1}} + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{F}^{\text{SE2}}. \quad (32)$$

2.3 FNM laminate element

Figure 3: 3D FNM laminate element

With the FNM ply and cohesive elements defined above, a FNM laminate element can be defined, such that the FNM ply and cohesive elements are SEs of the laminate element. Hence, multiple plies and interfaces are represented within such a laminate element, together with the matrix cracks, delamination and their intersections, represented respectively by the ply SEs and cohesive SEs as described in the previous sections. The construction of a FNM laminate element is straightforward. Let N_{nodePLY} indicates the number of nodes (both real and floating) of a FNM ply element, and $N_{\text{nodeINTERF}}$ the number of nodes (both real and floating) of a FNM cohesive element. A FNM laminate element for a laminate of n ply-blocks of different fibre angles would have the number of nodes, N_{nodeLAM} , to be:

$$N_{\text{nodeLAM}} = n \times N_{\text{nodePLY}}. \quad (33)$$

The i th FNM ply element would simply have the i th set of N_{nodePLY} nodes in its node array $\text{NodeArray}_{\text{PLY}i}$:

$$\text{NodeArray}_{\text{PLY}i}(j) = (i - 1) \times N_{\text{nodePLY}} + j, \text{ where } j = 1, 2, \dots, N_{\text{nodePLY}}. \quad (34)$$

The i th FNM cohesive element shares the top surface nodes of the i th FNM ply element and the bottom surface nodes of the $(i + 1)$ th FNM ply element. Therefore, it would have the following nodes in its node array $\text{NodeArray}_{\text{INTERF}i}$:

$$\text{NodeArray}_{\text{INTERF}i}(l) = \text{NodeArray}_{\text{PLY}i}(l + N_{\text{nodePLY}}/2), \quad (35)$$

$$\text{NodeArray}_{\text{INTERF}i}(l + N_{\text{nodeINTERF}}/2) = \text{NodeArray}_{\text{PLY}(i+1)}(l), \quad (36)$$

where $l = 1 \sim N_{\text{nodeINTERF}}/2$. With the above-defined connectivities, all the nodes in the FNM laminate element can be allocated to the respective ply and interface cohesive elements for their integrations as detailed in the previous sections. Their system matrices are then assembled back to those of the laminate element after the integration according to the connectivities in (35) and (36). Note that all the SEs are within the same FNM laminate element. The information of one SE is directly available to another. For example, the matrix crack coordinates of ply elements are directly available to the interface cohesive SEs, the latter can then do the corresponding partitions to explicitly represent the matrix crack edges on the interface, as described in section 2.2.

3 APPLICATION

Figure 4: A 3D FNM laminate element under transverse tension

A transverse tension problem on a 3-ply laminate of lay-up $[-30, 0, 30]$ is studied using a single FNM laminate element, constructed using the approach described in section 2. Figure 4(a) shows the geometry and the loading of the problem. A uniform tensile displacement loading is prescribed on the two transverse surfaces of the element. Figure 4(b) shows the predicted crack surfaces within the element. The color indicates the damage in the cohesive cracks, where the associated value is the stiffness degradation factor. Figure 4(c) shows the displacement field of the element. It can be seen that both matrix cracks and delamination are captured within the element, and that a clear discontinuous displacement field in each ply is represented. Note that the color in the interface cohesive elements indicates a degradation factor of 0.5. This is due to the fact that the boundary nodes of the cohesive elements are constrained from having any relative displacement from each other, and only the floating nodes (at the crack locations) can move relative to their corresponding nodes on the opposite surface. With the Newton-Cotes integration method used, this would cause that half the integration points in each cohesive SE reach delamination, which translates to an averaged degradation factor of 0.5 in the element.

For comparison, the same problem is applied to the case where all the FNM cohesive elements are replaced with standard cohesive elements, which do not partition with respect to the matrix cracks, and the result is shown in Figure 5(b). It can be seen that no delamination is predicted, which is expected as there is no driving mechanism to delaminate since all the boundary nodes constrained.

Figure 5 Comparison between FNM cohesive and standard cohesive element

4 CONCLUSIONS

A 3D Floating Node Method is developed to model progressive damage and failure in composite laminates. Specific FNM ply and cohesive elements for plies and interfaces of composite laminates are formulated. A FNM laminate element is constructed with respect to its lay-up, using the FNM ply and cohesive elements. The FNM laminate element is able to represent explicitly both the matrix cracks and the delamination, as well as their intersections. The application example shows that the FNM laminate is able to capture the local matrix crack/delamination interaction events.

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